

PHYSICAL, GEOMETRICAL, CHEMICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SOME SELECTED REINFORCING STEEL BARS FROM STEEL PLANTS

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Abstract: This study critically examined the quality of reinforcing steel bars in Nigeria due to frequent building collapses. It investigated five sizes (10-25 mm) from six local brands (A–F) for compliance with necessary standards. Testing included mechanical (tensile), hardness, chemical, geometrical, physical properties, and SEM-EDS analysis. Yield Strength showed significant variation, ranging from 360.96 MPa to 634.99 MPa. Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS) ranged from 573.62 MPa to 791.43 MPa, and Elongation showed adequate ductility (16.66% to 41.31%). Only sample A25 failed the NIS and ASTM yield strength standards. Only a few samples (A10, B10, B12, E20) met the stricter BS 4449 yield strength standard. All brands met the ASTM A706 and NIS 117 standards for UTS, but A10 and A20 failed the BS 4449 threshold. In terms of chemical composition (C, Mn, P, S, CEV), only Brand A consistently met all (BS 4449, NIS, ASTM A706) requirements. Brands B, C, D, E, and F showed inconsistent adherence to the required chemical composition standards

Keywords: Reinforcing steel bars, Spectromaxx Metal Analyser, Chemical composition, Carbon Equivalent Values (CEV), Mechanical properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

Steel is widely recognized as one of the most commonly used engineering materials for structural applications [1]. In both developed and developing countries, the steel industry is regarded as a key driver of industrialization and economic development [2, 3]. Its economic benefits stem from the relative simplicity of its manufacturing process and its abundance in the earth's crust [1]. Reinforced concrete structures among the most commonly constructed worldwide typically utilize a combination of concrete and steel reinforcing bars [4]. A reinforced concrete structure is a composite system, consisting of concrete and reinforcing steel. Concrete is made from a mixture of Portland cement, aggregates (such as rock, sand, or gravel), and water [4, 5, 6]. A successful combination of concrete and steel reinforcement, enables buildings and other structures to withstand specified loads without experiencing undue deformation [5]. For many years, steel has been a reliable and necessary component for strengthening concrete constructions. The foundation of reinforced concrete design is the idea that concrete and steel cooperate to withstand

applied stresses. A construction is categorized as reinforced concrete (RC) when steel bars are utilized as passive reinforcement [7]. A steel product having a round or nearly circular cross-section that may be embedded in concrete is commonly referred to as reinforcing steel [8].

According to Adetoro and Oladapo [9], steel reinforcement is extensively used in concrete works and modern structural developments. In Nigeria, reinforced concrete stands out as the most commonly used construction material, accounting for approximately 90% of all storey buildings constructed in the country [10, 11]. Within reinforced concrete construction, steel primarily serves to resist tensile and flexural stresses [12], highlighting its critical role in structural integrity. Consequently, the cost of steel reinforcement is a major consideration for contractors, builders, and prospective homeowners alike [13, 14].

Furthermore, the performance of reinforced concrete structures under cyclic loading relies heavily on the reinforcing steel bars demanding far more from the material than its basic structural function [15]. As Nigeria continues to develop, the

demand for new buildings and infrastructure is rapidly increasing [16]. Unfortunately, this growth has been accompanied by a rising incidence of structural failures and building collapses [17]. The Structural Failures and building collapse can be attributed to the following; Poor mixtures, Soil Textures, unskilled workers, Substandard Reinforcement Steel bars, etc. These failures have sparked renewed interest in evaluating the fundamental properties of reinforcing steel bars available in Nigerian markets, which are the primary sources of steel used in construction and structural projects [16, 17, 18]. Given the critical role of reinforcement in structural integrity, it is essential to verify the properties of steel bars before use in any structural application. Ensuring quality can significantly reduce or even prevent the occurrence of building and infrastructural failures, which often result in devastating loss of life and property. Therefore, regular testing and characterization of reinforcing steel have become increasingly important for safe and reliable construction [2].

Igibah [19] observed that the use of locally manufactured or factory-produced reinforcing steel bars made from scrap metal is increasingly common in Nigeria and across much of Africa. Currently, the majority of reinforcing steel bars used in Nigeria's construction industry are produced predominantly from scrap materials. This growing reliance on scrap as feedstock by steel rolling mill companies has had a detrimental impact on the quality of reinforcement bars in the country [4]. While issues related to poor structural design practices in Nigeria have received significant attention in recent years, numerous studies have identified the substandard quality of reinforcement steel as a major contributor to building collapses. Reinforcing steel plays a critical role in absorbing tensile and shear stresses within concrete structures [20, 21]. However, steel bars delivered to construction sites often sourced from various manufacturers frequently lack reliable and comprehensive information about their structural properties. This absence of transparency has created an environment conducive to the proliferation of substandard products. Furthermore, there is generally no consistent quality control process that extends from the point of manufacture to the final sale in the market [22].

The most crucial factor in determining the structural soundness of reinforced concrete structures is the stability of the buildings and civil infrastructure. To do this, high-quality reinforcing steel bars should be used in combination with sound structural analysis and design [23]. For built facilities for national growth to be sustainable and structurally

sound, high-quality reinforcing steel is essential [24]. Therefore, understanding the physical, geometrical, mechanical properties, as well as the percentage chemical composition of steel reinforcement bars is essential for ensuring the reliability and durability of structural systems. Comprehensive studies that address all of these characteristics over the whole range of bar sizes seem to be lacking, according to the reviewed literature. The majority of previous studies have concentrated on bars with diameters of 10 mm, 12 mm, and 16 mm [1, 2-7, 9-16], paying little or no attention to bigger sizes like 20 mm and 25 mm. We close this gap in this work by examining the Mechanical Properties, Hardness Values, % chemical composition and Microstructural Properties of reinforcing steel bars that measure 10 mm, 12 mm, 16 mm, 20 mm, and 25 mm. These bars are obtained from six distinct steel mills (designated A, B, C, D, E, and F).

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

This research work was carried out in June 2023–March 2025 at Abia, Enugu, Benin, Kaduna, Ogun, Oyo, Nigeria. Reinforcing steel bar samples locally produced from six different steel plants were obtained. The bars were identified using Standard Organization of Nigeria (SON) identification and classification marks [8, 25, 26, 27]. Five diameters (10, 12, 16, 20 and 25 mm) of the reinforcing steel bars were selected from each of the six steel plant. The samples were each coded based on the steel plant (A, B, C, D, E and F) and samples diameter (10, 12, 16, 20 and 25 mm). For example, samples from plant A were identified as A25, A20, and A10 with heat numbers of 23060255, 23060257 and 23080313 respectively. A represents the steel plant whereas 25, 20 and 10 represents the diameters. Similar approach was used for the identification of samples from other steel plants. B plant samples were identified as B16, B12 and B10 with heat numbers of 230705121, 230705123 and 23040615 respectively. And C12, D16, E20 and F25 were gotten from Kenyetta building material market, Enugu State in order to make sure that each diameter has two different brands for the assessments. There were five (5) specimens in each of the samples

2.1.1 Physical Properties

An assessment of reinforcing steel bars used in construction was carried out, focusing on samples obtained from six major manufacturers, designated as A, B, C, D, E, and F. The evaluation specifically examined the physical and geometric properties of the bars. Samples tested had nominal diameters of 10

mm, 12 mm, 16 mm, 20 mm, and 25 mm, as illustrated in Figure 2. The assessment involved several steps. First, the ends of each specimen were trimmed to obtain a well-defined length that could be measured accurately. Once the length was determined, the weight of each bar was recorded. Using these measurements, the mass per unit length was calculated. These values, along with the standard density of steel ($0.00785 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg/mm}^3$), were then used to compute the cross-sectional area, diameter, and gauge length of the bars using equations (1), (2), and (3).

$$Area = \frac{Mass}{Density \times Length} \quad [28]$$

(1)

$$Diameter = \sqrt{\frac{4 \times Area}{\pi}} \quad [28]$$

(2)

Where $\pi = 3.142$

$$Gauge \ Length \ L_o = 5.65\sqrt{Area} \quad [29]$$

(3)

2.1.2 Geometrical Properties

- i. **Rib height (h):** This was determined by placing the caliper's knife-edge across two adjacent ribs and extending the depth gauge until it made contact with the surface of the bar. The measurement were taken three times. One at the centre of each of the specimen and the other two measurement at the respective quarter points after which the average were taken [32].
- ii. **Rib spacing (c):** This was measured by positioning the outer jaws of the digital calipers between two neighboring transverse ribs. The measurement were taking by the length of eleven spaces after which the average were computed for each of the specimens [32].
- iii. **Rib Height per Rib Spacing (h/c):** This was computed from the parameters on BS 4449[8] standard as shown in Table 2. This is gotten dividing the rib heights h by the rib spacing c. And d stands for the Nominal diameter.

Table 1: Ranges for the rib parameters

Rib height, <i>h</i>	Rib spacing, <i>c</i>	Rib inclination, β
0.03 <i>d</i> to 0.15 <i>d</i>	0.4 <i>d</i> to 1.2 <i>d</i>	35° to 75°

Plate 1

2.2 Chemical Composition

The chemical analysis was carried out using Spectromaxx Metal Analyser with model no: MAXxLMF14 and serial number, 09001204 at Defence Industry Corporation of Nigeria(DICON) Laboratory in Kaduna State. The 25, 20, 16-mm-diameter samples were prepared to fit into the appropriate diameter standard orifice of tungsten carbide disk to be mounted on the machine as the Argon Gas was switched on. Nevertheless, the samples with lower diameters (10 and 12 mm) were integrated onto tungsten carbide disks that had holes of 10 and 12 mm in diameter. Before being installed on the machine, the samples were ground and polished to provide a flat, smooth surface devoid of impurities. The test were conducted on replicate counts of three for each of the brands after which average were taken for the twenty seven (27) elements. Following the presentation of the samples' average elemental percentage by weight (wt %) on a linked monitor, the carbon equivalent value (CEV) was calculated as shown in equation (7).

$$Carbon \ Equivalent \ Value = C + \frac{Mn}{6} + \frac{Cr+Mo+V}{5} + \frac{Ni+Cu}{15} \quad (7)$$

2.3 Tensile Test

As seen in Fig. 1, each test sample was carefully divided into five specimens, each measuring 500mm. A Universal Motion Incorporated Tensile Testing Machine, MUTC 100, with a 1000 KN capability, was used for the test in the University of Nigeria, Nsukka's Mechanical Engineering Workshop using 0.2% offset method as in illustrated in ASTM A370-24 [31] and ISO-15630-1[32]. The specimen underwent continuous tensile loading at 10mm/min until it fractured after being put on the tensile test apparatus. The test were administered on the five specimen, and the mean data were noted for improved test reliability.

2.4 Hardness Test

The hardness test was performed on samples (which comprises of Five (5) Specimens for each of the brands) cut from the tension-tested rebar. The test was conducted at the Defence Industry Corporation of Nigeria (DICON) Laboratory in Kaduna State using a Digital Micro Vickers Hardness Tester, Model: HVS-1000Z. The samples, which were 10 mm in height, were meticulously prepared by cleaning, grinding, and polishing. The test procedure involved applying a 4.904 N test load with a 3 kgf force and a 15-second dwell time to measure the micro-hardness across the cross-section of the samples, from the periphery to the core. Five measurements were recorded at a distance of 0.5 mm between consecutive indents. The test provided diagonal indentation values, which were then used to calculate the hardness values of different Conversions (like HRA, HRD and HRC).

$$VHN = 1.854 \frac{F}{D^2}$$

2.5 SEM EDS

SEM EDS were performed on steel samples A, B, C, D, E, and F to examine their surface morphology and their elemental weight composition. The samples, with sizes ranging from 12 mm to 25 mm (denoted as C12, B16, D16, E20, F25, and A25), were analyzed using a JEOL JSM 7600F SEM EDS Machine at the Material and Metallurgical Engineering Workshop of the University of Ibadan. This analysis focused on identifying surface roughness, irregularities, microvoids, inclusions, fracture features and elemental weight composition.

2.5.1 Sample preparation for SEM EDS

Samples from different steel plants (A-F) were first collected. These were then cut into 10mm lengths to ensure they fit properly within the SEM's specimen chamber. Following the cutting, the samples underwent grinding to prepare their surfaces for analysis. The prepared samples are rigidly mounted on a specimen stub, a specialized holder. To make them electrically conductive, the samples are coated with platinum. This coating is applied using

either low-vacuum sputter coating or high-vacuum evaporation. This conductive layer is crucial because it prevents the buildup of electrical charge on the sample, which could interfere with the analysis once mounted and coated, the samples are placed in the SEM's high-pressure chamber. This high-pressure environment serves a dual purpose: it neutralizes charge on the sample surface and amplifies the secondary electron signal, which improves image quality. For low-voltage SEM, a Field Emission Gun (FEG-SEM) is used. The FEG is preferred because it can produce a high-brightness electron beam with a small spot size even at low accelerating potentials, which is ideal for high-resolution imaging.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tables 2 gives a thorough summary of the experimental findings of the physical and geometric properties of the sampled steel reinforcing bars by combining the average measurement and computed data for the geometric properties of the steel reinforcing bars with diameters of 10 mm, 12 mm, 16 mm, 20 mm, and 25 mm. To ensure standard compliance and quality control in engineering and construction applications, physical and geometrical analysis are vital for comprehending the quality and diversity of the bars examined.

Table 2: Physical and Geometrical Properties of Reinforcement Steel bars

Brands/ Company	ML (Kg/m)	Deviation of ML (%)	Nominal Diameter (mm)	Diameter (mm)	Deviation from the nominal diameter (%)	Area (mm ²)	Gap between the transverse Ribs c (mm)	Depth of the ribs h (mm)	Depth of the ribs per spacing between the ribs h/c	BS 4449 Range For h/c
A10	0.541	87.88	10	9.368	6.3184	68.940	8.073	0.737	0.091	0.075 - 0.125
B10	0.452	73.25	10	8.558	14.424	57.522	5.905	0.789	0.134	0.075 - 0.125
B12	0.582	65.54	12	9.714	19.049	74.152	9.064	0.710	0.078	0.075 - 0.125
C12	0.532	59.91	12	9.288	22.621	67.748	11.690	0.749	0.064	0.075 - 0.125
B16	1.013	64.11	16	12.818	19.971	129.068	10.500	1.027	0.097	0.075 - 0.125
D16	1.044	66.08	16	13.104	18.103	133.012	13.501	0.907	0.067	0.075 - 0.125
A20	1.989	80.53	20	17.961	10.194	253.411	15.000	1.790	0.119	0.075 - 0.125
E20	1.575	63.77	20	15.987	20.078	200.695	16.391	1.523	0.092	0.075 - 0.125
A25	3.264	84.78	25	23.008	7.967	415.831	18.864	2.000	0.106	0.075 - 0.125
F25	3.522	91.40	25	23.900	4.400	448.709	13.464	1.309	0.097	0.075 - 0.125

The B10, B12, and B16 bars recorded average diameters of 8.558 mm, 9.714 mm, and 12.818 mm, with corresponding deviations of 14.424%, 19.049%, and 19.971%, respectively. Similarly, the C12, D16, and E20 bars had average diameters of 9.288 mm, 13.104 mm, and 15.987 mm, showing deviations of 22.621%, 18.103%, and 20.078%, respectively. The A20 bars had an average diameter of 17.961 mm, with a deviation of 10.194%. Among all the samples, the C12 bar exhibited the highest deviation at 22.621%, while the F25 sample had the lowest. This was followed by the A series samples (10 mm, 20 mm, and 25 mm), which also showed relatively low deviations.

Table 2 demonstrates that the reinforcing steel bars (A, B, C, D, E, and F) satisfied the rib height and rib spacing requirements of BS 4449-2005A2-2009. Additionally, as the nominal diameter rises for each brand, so do the rib height and spacing. The bars (excluding B10) also satisfied the rib height-to-spacing ratio standard of BS 4449-2005A2-2009 which is $0.075 < h/c < 0.125$.

Table 3: Elemental Compositions of Various Reinforcing bar samples

Element (Wt.%)	Samples									
	A25	F25	A20	E20	B16	D16	B12	D12	A10	B10
C	0.132	0.70	0.059	0.85	1.01	0.89	0.367	0.358	0.107	0.310
Si	0.220	0.300	0.162	0.125	3.52	0.59	0.223	0.291	0.162	0.201
Mn	1.00	2.02	0.91	0.373	3.09	>4.64	0.52	0.68	0.59	0.90
P	<0.0000	<0.0010	0.0049	0.017	0.025	0.025	0.014	0.0096	0.0061	0.0051
S	0.025	0.051	0.021	0.193	0.183	0.134	0.029	0.0022	0.034	0.026
Cr	0.401	0.57	0.298	0.093	0.65	0.79	0.174	0.218	0.470	0.344
Ni	0.046	0.091	0.060	0.148	7.41	0.149	0.095	0.093	0.087	0.072
Mo	0.022	0.059	0.015	0.298	0.073	0.060	0.016	0.013	0.0072	<0.0000
Al	0.049	0.045	0.0060	>8.83	0.048	0.108	0.011	0.017	0.017	0.0076
Cu	0.430	0.66	0.350	0.196	1.21	0.111	0.175	0.284	0.52	0.425
Co	<0.0000	0.015	0.0055	0.061	0.106	0.057	0.013	0.0096	0.016	0.0089
Ti	0.0100	0.013	<0.0000	0.020	0.027	0.026	<0.0000	<0.0000	<0.0000	<0.0000
Nb	0.034	0.040	0.019	0.059	0.090	0.081	<0.0000	0.0060	0.0072	0.0077
V	0.0051	0.454	0.0017	0.035	2.12	0.019	0.0023	<0.0000	<0.0000	<0.0000
W	0.028	0.122	0.030	0.331	0.58	0.59	0.022	0.029	0.039	0.025
Pb	<0.0000	0.040	<0.0000	>0.158	>0.189	>0.189	<0.0000	<0.0000	<0.0000	<0.0000
Mg	0.025	0.029	0.012	0.058	0.057	0.059	<0.0000	0.0040	0.011	0.0068
B	<0.0000	0.0028	0.0009	0.018	0.018	0.016	0.0025	0.0027	0.0024	0.0019
Sn	<0.0000	0.016	0.011	0.046	0.079	0.058	0.014	0.0096	0.016	0.011
Zn	0.119	>0.157	>0.068	>0.32	>0.81	>1.02	0.013	>0.066	>0.097	>0.133
As	<0.0000	<0.0010	<0.0000	0.039	0.031	0.026	0.0085	0.0037	<0.0000	<0.0000
Bi	<0.0000	<0.0020	<0.0000	<0.0000	>0.027	0.0048	0.0064	<0.0000	<0.0000	<0.0000
Ca	>0.030	>0.028	0.0059	>0.022	>0.018	>0.026	0.0040	0.0069	>0.016	0.0032
Ce	0.0100	0.027	<0.0000	0.087	0.124	0.112	<0.0000	0.0065	0.0041	<0.0000
Zr	<0.0000	<0.0010	<0.0000	<0.0000	<0.0000	<0.0000	<0.0000	<0.0000	<0.0000	<0.0000
La	0.039	0.052	0.023	0.142	0.185	0.175	<0.0000	0.021	0.037	0.0036
Fe	97.4	<94.5	<97.3%	<87.3	<78.3	<90.0	98.3	97.9	<97.4	<97.5

Figure 1: Plot of percentage carbon against Test Samples and samples

Figure 2: Plot of percentage carbon against Test Samples and samples

other significant residual elements found in samples sourced from various steel plants. Figure 1 illustrates the carbon content of the A samples, measured at 0.107%, 0.0590%, and 0.132% for the 10 mm, 20 mm, and 25 mm bars, respectively. Among these, the 20 mm bar exhibited the lowest carbon content. The carbon percentage for the 10 mm, 12 mm, and 16 mm bars in the B samples was 0.310%, 0.358%, and 1.01%, respectively. Carbon levels in samples C, D, E, and F were all noticeably higher than permitted limits. As indicated in Table 1, the sulfur (S) and phosphorus (P) concentrations in the A samples varied from 0.021 to 0.034% and 0.000 to 0.016%, respectively, over the 10 mm, 20 mm, and 25 mm bars. The B samples had phosphorus and sulfur concentrations ranging from 0.0089 to 0.025% and 0.026 to 0.183% for the 10 mm, 12 mm, and 16 mm diameters, respectively. Notably, the 16 mm B sample's sulfur concentration was higher than the acceptable threshold. While samples C and F remained within the standard range for sulfur, samples D and E showed elevated sulfur levels at 0.134% and 0.193%, respectively exceeding the limits set by NIS 117, BS 4449 [8], and ASTM [27]. However, all bars met the standard requirements for phosphorus content, as presented in Table 1. Regarding manganese, the highest concentration was found in the 16 mm bar from steel plant D, exceeding 4.64%. This was followed by the 16 mm B sample at 3.52%, and the 25 mm F sample at 2.02%.

The carbon content of the A (10 mm, 20 mm, and 25 mm), B (10 mm and 12 mm), and C (16 mm) steel bars analyzed in this study classifies them as either low- or medium-carbon steels, based on the criteria established by Roberts and Reza [27]. However, as illustrated in Figure 1, carbon content across samples from different steel plants lacked consistency when compared with various standards. This inconsistency highlights the adverse impact of using scrap materials in steel production, despite possible efforts to control carbon levels. Since carbon plays a major role in determining steel's mechanical characteristics, this variation might lead to notable variations in the steel bars' ductility and strength [18, 34]. Except for the B (16 mm), D (16 mm), and E (20 mm) samples, as shown in Table 5, sulfur and phosphorus known to be harmful components in reinforcing steel were largely below permitted values as per requirements [8, 25, 26, 27]. Some of the steel bars also exhibited manganese content below the recommended threshold, primarily due to elevated sulfur levels. Manganese is essential in counteracting the harmful effects of sulfur by forming manganese sulfide (MnS), a stable compound, instead of the undesirable and brittle iron sulfide (FeS), which

Table 3 summarizes the concentrations of key elemental constituents including carbon (C), manganese (Mn), silicon (Si), chromium (Cr), and

negatively affects mechanical properties. Despite some issues, all the samples complied with the standard phosphorus limits (Table 1), suggesting that they should generally exhibit good ductility [35]. As shown in Figure 2, the A series samples, along with B (12 mm) and C (12 mm), all maintained carbon equivalent values (CEV) within the recommended standards [8, 25, 26, 27]. In contrast, samples B (10 mm and 16 mm), C, E, and F exceeded the permissible CEV limits set by NIS 117, BS 4449, and ASTM A706. Finally, Table 3 reveals the presence of 27 different elemental constituents across the reinforcing steel bars of various diameters.

Figure 3: Yield strength of the reinforcing steel bar samples compared with some standards

Figure 4: Ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of the reinforcing steel bar samples compared with some standards

Figure 5: % elongation of the reinforcing steel bar samples compared with some standards

Table 4: Mechanical Properties of Reinforcement Steel Bars

Brand	Yield Stress (Mpa)	Ultimate		Hardness (HV)	Reference
		Tensile Stress (Mpa)	Elongation (%)		
A10	517.72	593.11	29.22	227.50	PS
B10	634.99	791.43	16.66	262.50	PS
B12	532.53	706.88	22.47	240.60	PS
C12	430.82	613.37	41.31	258.00	PS
B16	420.83	583.49	20.88	236.40	PS
D16	423.36	580.11	29.11	228.70	PS
A20	484.74	573.82	22.47	219.00	PS
E20	509.50	603.30	24.20	225.50	PS
A25	360.96	641.23	21.83	210.30	PS
F25	418.50	703.46	20.88	238.60	PS
US	566.00	713.80	10.03	295.38	[16]
NS	401.75	582.20	18.31	291.16	[16]
AS	500.00	624.00	13.02	255.75	[16]

Note: Ps stands for Present study

The yield and ultimate tensile strengths of reinforcing steel bars of various diameters, sourced from different steel plants, were assessed against standard benchmarks and are presented in Figures 3 and 4, respectively. Yield strength values ranged from 360.96 MPa to 634.99 MPa, while ultimate tensile strength values spanned from 573.62 MPa to 791.43 MPa across the different bar sizes. Figure 5 illustrates the percentage elongation for the bars, which ranged from 16.66% to 41.31%. Figure 6 shows the hardness values for the bars, based on diameter and manufacturing source, with values ranging from 14.80 to 23.68 HRC.

The yield point, which signifies the transition from elastic to plastic deformation, is used to determine a material's yield strength [35]. For reinforcing steel bars used in structural and construction applications, the required minimum yield strengths are set at 415 MPa by ASTM A706 [27], 500 MPa by BS 4449 [8], and 420 MPa by NIS 117 [25, 26]. All steel bar samples from plants A to F met the yield strength requirements of ASTM and

NIS 117, with the exception of sample A25, which recorded a yield strength of 360.96 MPa. However, as seen in Figure 3, only a small number of samples A10, B10, B12, and E20 achieved yield strengths of 517.72 MPa, 634.99 MPa, 532.53MPa, and 509.50 MPa, respectively, meeting the more exacting BS 4449 norm. The existence of different residual components, a problem frequently linked to the use of scrap metal as the main feedstock in the manufacturing of steel, is probably the cause of the inconsistency in satisfying the BS 4449 standards [34, 36, 37]. The variations in ultimate tensile strength (UTS) among the steel bar samples are depicted in Figure 4. According to NIS 117 [25,26], BS 4449 [8], and ASTM A706 [28], UTS the highest stress a material can withstand before breaking must be more than 500 MPa, 600 MPa, or 550 MPa. Although every sample met ASTM A706 and NIS 117 UTS criteria, only two samples A10 (593.11 MPa) and A20 (573.82 MPa) did not meet the BS 4449 threshold.

Comparative analysis shows that the UTS values obtained in this study are consistent with those reported by Mohammed and Danso. [16]. Enough UTS is crucial for reinforcing steel bars since it increases their capacity to tolerate strain and maintain structural integrity by preventing fractures. Because a greater UTS indicates stronger steel that can withstand bigger loads before failing, this attribute is essential when selecting rebars for construction [38]. Significant variations in the mechanical properties and chemical composition of steel bars were observed even among samples from the same manufacturer. Nevertheless, steel bars with a same percentage of elongation exhibit similar ductility. Table 4 elucidates that the percentage elongation results from this experiment are in good agreement with those from other investigations. All of the tested steel bars met the required ductility standards. Ductility is necessary for reinforced concrete structures to perform effectively. Inadequate ductility of steel bars can have detrimental effects on the flexibility and resilience of structural elements [39]. As seen in Figure 5, all tested steel bars exhibit adequate ductility, enabling them to withstand uneven plastic deformations and avoid buckling or early tensile fracture under service conditions.

Hardness is defined as a material's resistance to abrasion [2, 35]. As illustrated in Figure 6, The Hardness Value varies from 210.30HV to 262.50 HV. A25 Brand possess the values of 210.30 HV while B10 possess the highest value of 262.50HV. Alabi and Onyeji [36] stressed that steel bars used in structural and building applications must have a

sufficient hardness, and that a higher carbon content in reinforcing steel usually corresponds with increased hardness. Insufficient hardness can compromise the performance of steel under service conditions. The inconsistent hardness levels of steel bars from the same and separate manufacturing facilities were a noteworthy finding in this investigation. The presence of hazardous and residual components introduced during the utilization of scrap metal as the main raw material in the manufacturing of steel is probably the cause of this heterogeneity. Despite satisfying elongation criteria, many reinforcing steel bars advertised as high-yield steel in Nigeria's Federal Capital Territory (FCT) were really mild steel and did not adhere to BS 4449 [8] chemical composition norms, according to Apeh [40]. Similar to this, Buliaminu [41] noted significant differences in the chemical composition, elongation, hardness, and tensile strength of steel bars made from scrap, specifically for ST44-2 and ST66-2 grades.

Scan Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Plate 2

Plate 3

Plate 4

Plates 2, 3, and 4 show a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) analysis of steel samples. Each plate features an SEM micrograph alongside its corresponding EDS compositional analysis and a graph of elemental distribution. The SEM images are shown at three different magnifications: X9000, X10, 000, and X12, 000. The SEM micrographs reveal the steel's morphology, which consists of pearlite (dark areas), a ferrite matrix (light areas), and various defect-like spots. The elemental distribution

graphs and EDS analysis demonstrate the connection between the chemical composition and the visual morphology. The relative weight concentration of each component in the reinforcing steel bars is shown by the height of the spikes on the graph. The quantity of pearlite in plain carbon steel grows together with the carbon concentration, giving the steel a darker colour. The observed defects, such as segregations, pinholes, and inclusions, are common issues from liquid steel treatment and can reduce the steel's ductility under stress. The most likely reason for the reduced elongation at fracture in this sample is the grip slip that occurred during the initial tensile test [45, 46, 47]

Table 7: Summary of the Reinforcing Bars Experimental Investigations Results

Brand	Mass per Unit Length (Kg/m)	Rib Geometry (h/c)	Chemistry										Upper Yield Stress (Mpa)	Ultimate Tensile Stress (Mpa)	Elongation (%)	Hardness (HRC)
			%C	%Mn	%Cr	%Mo	%V	%Ni	%Cu	CEV						
A10	0.54	0.09	0.11	0.99	0.47	0.01	<0.00	0.09	0.52	0.4079	517.72	593.11	29.22	14.08		
B10	0.45	0.13	0.31	0.90	0.34	<0.00	<0.00	0.07	0.43	0.5619	634.99	791.43	16.66	23.62		
B12	0.58	0.08	0.37	0.52	0.17	0.02	0.00	0.10	0.18	0.51	532.53	706.88	22.47	22.62		
C12	0.53	0.06	0.36	0.68	0.22	0.01	<0.00	0.09	0.28	0.516	430.82	613.37	41.31	23.68		
B16	1.01	0.10	1.01	3.09	0.65	0.07	2.12	7.41	1.21	2.6683	418.50	703.46	20.88	20.38		
D16	1.04	0.07	0.89	>4.64	0.79	0.06	0.02	0.15	0.11	1.8561	423.36	580.11	29.11	18.76		
A20	1.99	0.12	0.06	0.91	0.30	0.02	0.00	0.06	0.35	0.2419	484.74	573.82	22.47	13.82		
E20	1.58	0.09	0.85	0.37	0.09	0.30	0.04	0.15	0.20	1.0203	509.50	603.30	24.20	18.14		
A25	3.26	0.11	0.13	1.00	0.40	0.02	0.01	0.05	0.02	0.416	360.96	641.23	21.83	14.80		
F25	3.52	0.10	0.177	2.02	0.57	0.06	0.45	0.09	0.06	1.4095	418.50	703.46	20.88	20.64		

4 CONCLUSIONS

The physical, geometrical, chemical, and mechanical properties of the reinforcing steel bars were evaluated, and the results revealed that most of the samples failed to meet the recommended standards especially with respect to their physical and geometrical attributes. The reinforcing steel bars included twenty-seven (27) significant, residual, and deleterious components, according to chemical analysis. The mechanical characteristics of the steel bars were found to be affected to differing degrees by changes in the carbon equivalent values (CEVs), manganese, silicon, sulfur, phosphorus, and carbon contents. The analysis also revealed that several samples had chemical components that were within the suggested range, qualifying them for use in building and structural applications. In summary, a few of the steel bar samples met the required levels of carbon, manganese, nickel, sulfur, phosphorus, and their carbon equivalents of these essential elements. Their appropriateness for usage in structural applications was further confirmed by the fact that their yield strength, ultimate tensile strength, and elongation all satisfied the necessary requirements. And lastly, the morphology and the elemental weight concentration were displayed using SEM EDS machine.

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